

EFFECT OF STOCHASTICITY ON THE GROWTH OF THE ∞ -PARENT SLFV PROCESS - SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION FILE

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Supplementary Information A. A SIMULATION-BASED EXPLORATION OF THE LIMITING
BEHAVIOUR OF τ_x AND σ_x

A.1. Setting 1 - Square reproduction events.

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^\tau/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.1. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 1, for reproduction events with constant shape parameters $(a, a) = (0.2, 0.2)$.

A.2. Setting 2 - Rare extreme reproduction events.

Setting 2 - $n = 2$

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^{\tau}/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.2. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 2, for a distribution of shape parameters given by $\mu^{(2)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 3$

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^\tau/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.3. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 2, for a distribution of shape parameters given by $\mu^{(3)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 4$

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^\tau/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.4. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 2, for a distribution of shape parameters given by $\mu^{(4)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 5$

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^\tau / 2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.5. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 2, for a distribution of shape parameters given by $\mu^{(5)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 6$

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^{\tau}/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.6. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 2, for a distribution of shape parameters given by $\mu^{(6)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 7$

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^\tau/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.7. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 2, for a distribution of shape parameters given by $\mu^{(7)}$.

A.3. Setting 3 - Mixture of reproduction events.

Setting 3 - Mixture 1

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^{\tau}/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.8. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 3, for a combination of distribution of shape parameters given by "Mixture 1" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 2

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^\tau/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.9. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 3, for a combination of distribution of shape parameters given by "Mixture 2" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 3

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^{\tau}/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.10. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 3, for a combination of distribution of shape parameters given by "Mixture 3" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 4

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^\tau/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.11. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 3, for a combination of distribution of shape parameters given by "Mixture 4" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 5

(A) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\tau_x]$ obtained using simulations, and identification of the inverse ν^{-1} of the expansion speed by a linear regression performed on the second half of the graph (*i.e.*, on values of x such that $x \geq \delta i_{\max}^{\tau}/2$.)

(B) Plot of $x \rightarrow \mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$, using the approximation of $\mathbb{E}[\sigma_x - \tau_x]$ obtained using simulations.

FIGURE A.12. Exploration of the limiting behaviour of τ_x and σ_x in Setting 3, for a combination of distribution of shape parameters given by "Mixture 5" in Table ??.

Supplementary Information B. SIMULATION-BASED IDENTIFICATION OF THE SCALING OF THE VARIANCE OF τ_x AND σ_x WHEN $x \rightarrow +\infty$

B.1. Setting 1 - Square reproduction events.

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.1. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are constant and equal to $(a, a) = (0.2, 0.2)$.

B.2. Setting 2 - Rare extreme reproduction events.

Setting 2 - $n = 2$

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.2. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to $\mu^{(2)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 3$

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.3. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to $\mu^{(3)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 4$

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.4. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to $\mu^{(4)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 5$

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.5. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to $\mu^{(5)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 6$

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.6. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to $\mu^{(6)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 7$

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.7. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to $\mu^{(7)}$.

B.3. Setting 3 - Mixture of reproduction events.

Setting 3 - Mixture 1

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.8. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to the combination of distributions given by "Mixture 1" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 2

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.9. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to the combination of distributions given by "Mixture 2" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 3

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.10. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to the combination of distributions given by "Mixture 3" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 4

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.11. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to the combination of distributions given by "Mixture 4" in Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 5

(A) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\tau_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

(B) Log-log plot of $\text{Var}(\sigma_x)$ as a function of x using the approximation obtained using simulations, and identification of the scaling exponent.

FIGURE B.12. Identification of the scaling exponent for the variance of τ_x and σ_x , when shape parameters are sampled according to the combination of distributions given by "Mixture 5" in Table ??.

Supplementary Information C. IDENTIFICATION OF TWO DISTINCT SCALING REGIMES FOR THE TRANSVERSE FLUCTUATIONS OF THE FRONT LOCATION

C.1. Setting 1 - Square reproduction events.

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.1. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters constant and equal to $(a, a) = (0.2, 0.2)$.

C.2. Setting 2 - Rare extreme reproduction events.

Setting 2 - $n = 2$

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.2. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to $\mu^{(2)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 3$

Transverse fluctuations - First stage

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

Transverse fluctuations - Second stage

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.3. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to $\mu^{(3)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 4$

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.4. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to $\mu^{(4)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 5$

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.5. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to $\mu^{(5)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 6$

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.6. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to $\mu^{(6)}$.

Setting 2 - $n = 7$

Transverse fluctuations - First stage

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

Transverse fluctuations - Second stage

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.7. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to $\mu^{(7)}$.

C.3. Setting 3 - Mixture of reproduction events.

Setting 3 - Mixture 1

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.8. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to "Mixture 1" from Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 2

Transverse fluctuations - First stage

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

Transverse fluctuations - Second stage

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.9. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to "Mixture 2" from Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 3

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.10. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to "Mixture 3" from Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 4

Transverse fluctuations - First stage

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

Transverse fluctuations - Second stage

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.11. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to "Mixture 4" from Table ??.

Setting 3 - Mixture 5

(A) Scaling regime in the first stage of the expansion, before the front has moved away entirely from its initial location.

(B) Scaling regime in the second stage of the expansion. The scaling exponent is close to the exponent of $1/3$ characteristic of stochastic growth models belonging to the KPZ universality class.

FIGURE C.12. Identification of two distinct scaling regimes for the transverse fluctuations of the front location, corresponding to before (in blue) and after (in green) the front has moved away entirely from its initial location. Simulation performed with shape parameters sampled according to "Mixture 5" from Table ??.